

Electricity Demand Mapping from Open-Source data (EDeMOS): a new methodology applied to Zambia

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Abstract

Spatially resolved energy systems modelling is increasingly used to provide more accurate insights into electrification planning and infrastructure development. This study presents a novel, open-source methodology for spatially resolved characterisation of electricity consumption in any given geography, and demonstrates this method on the case-study region of Zambia. By considering the geographical distribution of population centres, wealth and industrial activities, the methodology generates a spatially resolved electricity consumption map for buildings and industry. This detailed map can underpin the development of spatially explicit energy system models, facilitating informed decisions on grid infrastructure requirements, optimisation of electrification pathways, analysis of socio-economic impacts of energy transitions, supporting more equitable energy access in Zambia and other low- and middle-income countries.

Keywords:

Electricity consumption, Geographic Information Systems (GIS), open-source energy modelling, building footprints, open data, DHS, LMIC, Zambia, high-resolution mapping

1. Introduction

Accurate energy demand assessments are essential for effective energy planning and investment decisions, particularly in the context of expanding electricity access in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs). Increasingly, energy systems models incorporate higher spatial and temporal resolution (Moksnes, Howells, and Usher 2024; Brinkerink, Mayfield, and Deane 2024), because such granular approaches can produce significantly more accurate results than models with a coarser resolution (Brinkerink, Mayfield, and Deane 2024; Yliruka, Moret, and Shah 2023; Jalil-Vega and Hawkes 2018). For instance, spatial resolution can significantly impact the final results of energy system models as shown in the UK examples for electrification planning (Yliruka, Moret, and Shah 2023; Charitopoulos et al. 2023). This increasing emphasis on spatial detail in energy system models highlights the broader importance of spatially resolved energy demand data.

Beyond simply improving model accuracy, such data are crucial for a wider range of applications, including urban and rural planning (Keirstead and Calderon 2012), understand energy transition process for more effective policies (Caragliu and Graziano 2022), and analysing the socio-economic distributional impacts of energy policies (Balta-Ozkan, Watson, and Mocca 2015). Understanding the spatial distribution of electricity demand is thus crucial not only for optimizing grid planning but also for better planning of clean cooking pathways (Khavari et al. 2023) or identifying economic

opportunities linked to productive uses of energy (ESMAP 2023). In addition, mitigation and adaptation planning is increasingly being integrated into multi-level governance structures (provinces, counties, municipalities, etc) (Maharjan 2024), requiring spatial data to support analyses at these different levels (Hofbauer, McDowall, and Pye 2022).

The development of such granular models relies heavily on high-quality and spatially resolved data, which is becoming increasingly available thanks to advancements in Geographic Information Systems (GIS) (Mentis et al. 2017; Phillips et al. 2023; Zhang et al. 2024). For instance, renewable potentials are available at a very spatially disaggregated resolution with the global wind and solar atlas (Davis et al. 2023; Solargis 2024), which can be used to inform the resource/supply component of spatially disaggregated power system models. However, the spatial granularity of the demand component in those models, is understudied.

Developing spatially resolved energy system models is challenging, particularly due to the limited availability of high-quality spatial data—an issue that is especially pronounced in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs). Modelling tools like OnSSET¹ (Mentis et al. 2017) rely on granular demand assessment in un-electrified settlements. Typically, population distribution layers are used as a proxy of energy needs at a local level, a methodology that has limitations. Having a more complete picture of current electricity demand and future demand at a local level can improve electricity planning results, as shown by (Moksnes, Howells, and Usher 2024) in the Kenyan example.

A high spatial resolution necessitates, as a first requirement, an energy balance. The first step is thus to provide a mapping of current electricity demand, which can then be used as a basis for future energy service demand projections. While several studies have investigated this problem, they usually focus only on one sector, and they often are not specific to the LMIC context. For instance, in the buildings sector, energy demand assessments are usually performed at the household level and these household averages are used directly for projections, but they can also be disaggregated by income deciles (Baltruszewicz, Steinberger, Ivanova, et al. 2021; Baltruszewicz, Steinberger, Owen, et al. 2021) or for different consumer types (Riva et al. 2019). Many energy demand assessments at a high spatial resolution rely on smart meter systems, which provide real-time consumption levels, in particular for gas and electricity (Taylor et al. 2014; Wu et al. 2023). For instance, spatially resolved heat demand has been used to assess district heating potential (Gils et al. 2013; Nielsen and Möller 2013) or heating infrastructure requirements (Jalil-Vega and Hawkes 2018; Meha et al. 2021) but they are often explored in the case of developed countries. However, smart meter systems are still not widely installed in LMIC countries (IEA 2023b), though there are some initiatives that support their development (Ndigwe 2022; Lusaka Times 2020). Thus, studies still usually harness information provided by utility or pre-paid meters, for instance in Kenya (Fobi et al. 2018). National surveys can also be used to assess energy demand, but their spatial resolution is often coarse (Mbaka 2022).

To avoid the problem of lack of direct energy measurement, satellite base night-time light (NTL) data can offer a helpful alternative. For instance, electricity consumption has been assessed at the country level (Tripathy et al. 2018; Falchetta and Noussan 2019) or at the province level in China (Xiao et al. 2018) thanks to NTL. More spatially disaggregated results have been obtained for electricity (Shi et al. 2016; Chen et al. 2022) but the validation of the results is based at the country level and not necessarily done in the context of Sub-Saharan Africa. NTL data have also been used to assess other indicators such as GDP (Chen et al. 2022) or wealth index (McCallum et al. 2022). Finally, (Falchetta et al. 2019) developed a methodology using NTL data, gridded population and land

¹ OpeN Source Spatial Electrification Tool (OnSSET) (<https://github.com/OnSSET/onsset>)

scans to derive spatially resolved data on electricity access rates and potential consumption tiers for sub-Saharan African countries.

Some spatially disaggregated assessment focuses on specific sub-sectors of energy demand, usually on cooling or heating demand for households. (Moya et al. 2022; 2023) use national datasets from Ecuador to compute, at a highly spatially disaggregated resolution, several drivers for energy consumption in the residential sector such as population density space cooling demand and water heating demand. (Falchetta and Mistry 2021) also assess a highly spatially resolved cooling demand to evaluate different electrification scenarios in sub-Saharan Africa. However, the baseline demand is only computed based on tier access consumptions. Beyond spatial resolution, studies have also assessed the temporal resolution of the energy demand. (Sachs et al. 2019) produces temporally and spatially resolved demand profiles for heat and cooling demand in the residential sectors based on gridded data for temperature and population as well as energy balance from the International Energy Agency (IEA). (Staffell, Pfenninger, and Johnson 2023) assess hourly heating and cooling demand as well as at a highly disaggregated spatial scale. However, their model calibration relies on smart meter data primarily from developed countries, potentially overlooking specificities of LMICs.

Beyond current energy demand levels, identifying potential demand growth (and latent demand) is crucial, especially in the sub-Saharan Africa context, as lack of present-day demand is often the result of lack of energy access, and the grid infrastructure needs to be designed foreseeing future demand growth. Thus, some studies also focus on assessing the latent demand in areas lacking energy access (Mentis et al. 2019; Fobi and Mugenyi 2021; Lee et al. 2019; Falchetta et al. 2021). Some of these models (Lee et al. 2019; Falchetta et al. 2021) rely on very detailed input data in order to model different consumer types, which are then combined to assess the total electricity demand at high spatial resolution.

Finally, machine learning (ML) algorithms offer a promising avenue to assess energy demand at a high spatial resolution. Some techniques are being developed to assess the demand at the building level but they often require very detailed input data coming from utility meters to train the model (Lee 2023; 2024), which is difficult to access on a large-scale basis, and especially in an LMIC context. (Ratledge et al. 2022) use ML on satellite imagery to assess electricity access impact on local livelihoods. (Lee et al. 2021) develops probabilistic electricity demand forecasts, but the methods are applied at the national level, and results are only available for a handful of countries via Open Energy Maps (Uganda, Ghana and Senegal).

Regarding the industry sector, most existing studies operate at a relatively aggregated level. For instance, (Tyrallis, Mamassis, and Photis 2017) assess electricity demand for multiple sectors, including domestic and industrial sectors, but their analysis is limited to the NUTS3 level (Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics) in Greece, which is not highly spatially disaggregated. (Eggimann, Hall, and Eyre 2019) also provides a disaggregated demand assessment for multiple sectors including industry, but it remains at Local Authority Districts (LADs) in the UK. (Aramendia et al. 2023) provides energy consumption pathways for the mining sector at the global level based on different socio-economic scenarios.

Similarly, research specifically focused on mining in LMICs don't include a comprehensive assessment of spatial energy demand. While (Rahimpour Golroudbary et al. 2022) analyse cobalt energy consumption, they do not address spatial disaggregation, and provide results for 145 regions in the world. (Lèbre, Sharma, and Corzo Remigio 2024) provide a valuable global dataset for mining projects, but their analysis focuses on local disclosures and does not directly assess energy consumption. (Moreno-Leiva et al. 2024) analyses, in great detail, the different production processes

in the Chilean copper industry but remains at a very aggregated spatial resolution by considering only one single production facility.

A significant fraction of these previous studies is focused on countries from the global North and are not specific to the LMIC context. Moreover, they often cover only some energy vectors, and do not assess the total electricity consumption. Some rely heavily on smart meter data or disaggregated input data assumptions, limiting their replicability in other contexts. This work aims to address these limitations by presenting a new methodological approach for electricity demand mapping with a focus on the spatial component. More specifically, the suggested approach integrates open datasets such as building footprints, population distribution, night-time light data, mining locations and publicly available survey instruments and statistical reports to estimate electricity needs at local level. We test the methodology in Zambia; however, it can be replicable for most LMICs. Our approach adheres to open-source principles, allowing transparency for easy replication and adaptation across various African countries. Thus, this contribution provides a valuable tool for researchers and policymakers, including those seeking to develop more granular and accurate energy system models for improved electrification planning in the region.

2. Method

The method developed in this study aims to assess the total electricity consumption for each subsector including residential, services and industry at a highly spatially resolved resolution. The spatial unit of analysis is a hexagon, which provides the flexibility to modify the granularity of the analysis based on data availability and needs of the application. Each component assessment relies on combining highly spatially resolved dataset with data gathered at a national level (Figure 1 and Table 7 in the Supplementary Materials). The year of analysis is 2019.

Figure 1 Schematic representation of the methodological approach for estimating electricity demand in each sector leveraging GIS and non-GIS data.

The first step is to map the country with hexagons (Figure 2). The geographic signature of a country and its administrative divisions is mapped using the Global Administrative Areas (GADM) database². The country is then divided into hexagons using the H3 standard (level 7) of around 5.16 km² per cell (Uber Technologies 2024). Each hexagon cell has its own identifier (ID) number, which means that the coordinate reference system (CRS) projection does not affect the hexagon perimeter. It also allows an easier aggregation or disaggregation of outputs based on the intended granularity of analysis.

Figure 2 Zambia's administrative map divided into H3 hexagons using granularity level equal to 7, which yields around 125,000 hexagon cells for the entire country, each approximately 5.16 km² in area³.

2.1. Residential methodology: a bottom-up approach

The electricity consumption for residential buildings is assessed by first estimating the number of households with access to electricity in each hexagon cell, then estimating the average annual electricity consumption for each electrified household using the relative wealth index of that cell, then multiplying the two values. The two steps are described in more detail below; the datasets needed include the following:

² <https://gadm.org/data.html>

³ <https://h3geo.org/docs/core-library/restable/>

- a. **Number of households:** the number of households in each administrative division (province and/or district) derived from census data, available via the Zambia Statistics Agency (Zamstats 2022).
- b. **Number of buildings:** estimated via a raster layer provided by WorldPop (Dooley et al. 2021) with a resolution of $\sim 100\text{m}$. Note that the number of buildings is informed from building footprints layer provided by (Ecopia.AI and Maxar Technologies 2020).
- c. **Urbanization status:** delineation between urban and rural areas as provided by WorldPop (Dooley et al. 2021).
- d. **Electrification rate:** the probability of an area having electricity access as provided by the High Resolution Electricity Access (HREA) data set (Brian and Zachary 2023) at a resolution of 15 arcsec grid ($\sim 400\text{m}$).

Note that (b), (c), and (d) are available for many LMIC in Sub-Saharan Africa, while (a) can be typically obtained from the statistical office in each country. If this data is not available in the country, the number of households in rural and urban areas could alternatively be obtained via the UN Population Division⁴. The urban/rural split in each subregion would then not be known, but the total number of households can still be assessed for each cell.

2.1.1. Step 1: Assessing the number of households with electricity access

The first step aims to estimate the number of households with electricity access in each hexagon cell, based on the number of buildings and national statistics on the number of households. If the total number of households is available at the province level, the number of households in each cell can be adjusted to fit the province statistics. To do so, the share of residential building is assessed at the province level, which can then be applied in each cell to estimate the number of households. Otherwise, a similar analysis can be directly performed at the national level. We describe below the first case, as Zambia provides statistics at the province level.

Analysis at the province level

Based on the number of buildings in each province and the number of households, the aim is to determine the share of residential buildings in each province. First, the number of households in each province in each area type (urban/rural) must be assessed as it is not directly given by the statistics. Census data (a) provide the total number of households and the urban-rural population distribution by province ($P_{u,p}$, $P_{r,p}$), and at the national level, but does not provide the total number of households in urban and in rural areas per province. To assess these numbers, we thus need to assess the proportion of urban versus rural households in each province. While we can determine the average household size for each province (number of people per household), the available data does not provide separate household size estimates specifically for urban and rural areas within each province, which is essential for our analysis.

To address this, we first get the population size and the number of households by province as well as the average household size for urban and rural areas and at the national level (Figure 3 – Step 1), respectively noted S_u , S_r and S_a . We then calculate the average household size by province $S_{a,p}$ and the ratio between the household size for urban and rural areas and the average at the national level (Figure 3 – Step 2). Finally, assuming this national urban-to-rural household size ratio applies

⁴ <https://population.un.org/wpp/Download/Standard/Population/>

uniformly across provinces, we apply it to estimate separate average household sizes for urban and rural areas within each province ($S_{u,p}$, $S_{r,p}$) (Figure 3– Step 3).

Figure 3 Workflow used to determine the average household size per province for urban and rural households separately.

The total number of rural and urban households in each province ($HH_{r,p}$, $HH_{u,p}$) can then be determined by dividing the total population of each province ($P_{r,p}$, $P_{u,p}$) available in the census data (a) to the calculated average rural and urban household size for that province ($S_{r,p}$, $S_{u,p}$).

By assuming the number of households per residential building in rural areas (N_r), the share of residential buildings in each province in rural areas $Share_{res}B_{r,p}$ is computed with the following formula:

$$Share_{res}B_{r,p} = \frac{resB_{r,p}}{B_{r,p}} = \frac{HH_{r,p}}{N_r \cdot B_{r,p}} \quad (1)$$

With:

- $resB_{r,p}$: total number of residential buildings in rural areas in the province p
- $B_{r,p}$: total number of buildings in rural areas in the province p
- N_r : number of households per residential building in rural areas, set as 1⁵

A similar equation is applied to urban areas with N_u , number of households per residential building in urban areas, set as 1.2⁶.

Analysis at the cell level

After determining the provincial residential building shares, the analysis is refined to the hexagon level. WorldPop provides an estimate of the urbanization status (c) within each cell of our analysis; we calculate that using the median value of all pixels within the area of interest, as well as the

⁵ Following similar assumptions adopted in [PeanutButter](#), WorldPop data (WorldPop 2018)

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number of buildings. Thus, for each hexagon hex , we can estimate the total number of residential buildings (cf. equation (2) in the rural case), by multiplying the total number of buildings B from WorldPop (b) by the share of residential buildings, assessed previously, given its urbanization status from (c) (rural r or urban u) and its province location p .

$$resB_{hex} = B_{hex} * Share_{resB_{r,p}} \quad (2)$$

To estimate households per cell, the number of residential buildings is multiplied by the average number of households per residential building N_r or N_u . Finally, the estimated number of households per cell is multiplied by the cell-specific probability of having electricity access p_A provided by (d) (cf. equation (3) in the rural case). However, for urban areas, as the probability of having electricity access is always near 1, a correction factor of 0.85 was introduced to end up with an urban access rate in line with the values provided by other institutions (see values in Table 9).

$$HHaccess_{hex} = resB_{hex} * N_r * p_A \quad (3)$$

2.1.2.Step 2: Assess the energy consumption per household

The second step aims to assess the average annual electricity consumption for each electrified household using the relative wealth index of that cell. The following datasets are used:

- e. **Demographic and Health Survey** (DHS survey) 2018 (Zambia Statistics Agency, Ministry of Health (MOH) Zambia, and ICF 2020)
- f. **Relative wealth index** (Data for Good at Meta 2021; Chi et al. 2022) noted rwi thereafter

Analysis at the national level

The DHS survey gathers data from a representative sample of households across the country, with additional breakdowns at the regional level and by urban and rural areas (Zambia Statistics Agency, Ministry of Health (MOH) Zambia, and ICF 2020, chap. 2). Along with the wealth index (noted wi thereafter), the survey also provides detailed information on household characteristics, including data on household possessions:

- | | |
|----------------------|-------------------|
| - Electricity access | - Computer |
| - Radio | - Washing machine |
| - Mobile telephone | - Air conditioner |
| - Television | - Microwave |
| - Refrigerator | |

Each appliance is associated with a level of energy consumption (see Table 1), which also depends on the household tier. This table is based on the ESMAP report on energy access (Bhatia and Angelou 2015) and (MECS 2020) (see Appendix Table 8 for the details). The associated tiers are attributed based on the appliances ownership and if the household has electricity access or not. For instance, if a household owns only a television, it will be associated to tier 2, but if it also possesses a washing machine, it falls into tier 3.

Table 1 Average annual consumption in kWh for a set of appliances adjusted from (Bhatia and Angelou 2015; MECS 2020)

Appliance/Tier	1	2	3	4	5
Other electricity ⁷	4	136	324	870	1302
Mobile telephone	2	8	8	8	8
Radio	2	16	16	16	16
Television	0	40	80	80	80
Microwave	0	0	100	100	100
Washing machine	0	0	250	250	250
Refrigerator	0	0	0	900	900
Air conditioner	0	0	0	0	2000

We then compute the resulting household's energy consumption E_{HH} by adding up the energy consumption e_i for all of the appliances i from the relevant tier, multiplied by their availability in the household $a_{i,HH}$ (binary value, 0 if not owned and 1 if owned) and adjusting the total according to the number of people in the household, n_{HH} :

$$E_{HH} = \left(\frac{n_{HH}}{n_0}\right)^\alpha \sum_i a_{i,HH} * e_i$$

(4)

The nominal household size, n_0 , is the number of household members that is assumed for the appliance energy consumption values in Table 1. We adopt $n_0 = 4$. The parameter α represents how strongly electricity use depends on the household size. As far as the authors are aware, specific studies assessing this exact relationship are not available. We adopt $\alpha = 0.4$, which corresponds to two people using about a third more electricity than one person in the same house, and a family of 5 using almost half as much again.

Thus, we obtain a new dataset derived from the DHS survey, which provides estimated energy consumption of households for a given wealth index and location (rural or urban area).

Analysis at the cell level

To apply these household energy consumption estimates to the hexagon cells, we create a "simulated" group of households from the DHS survey dataset for each cell, such that the group has an average wealth index wi^8 and fraction of households with electricity access ("access rate") that are approximately equal to the equivalent values for the cell. This is achieved with a normal probability selection function, centred so as to achieve the desired mean wi value and with a standard deviation of 1 (in units of wi ; variations in this choice do not significantly affect any results).

⁷ Other electricity usage includes small appliances such as lighting. Higher tiers encompass additional appliances not listed above, such as computers.

⁸ Rwi refers to the relative wealth index provided by (Chi et al. 2022) while wi refers to the wealth index provided by the DHS survey.

To ensure that each simulated group has an access rate appropriate for its cell, the survey household sample is split into two subsamples, with and without access. Each group then draws from these in the appropriate ratio to produce the given access rate for its cell.

Because the number of households in most cells greatly exceeds the size of the DHS survey, the simulated groups were of a smaller fixed size that still captures the diversity of possible households whilst producing repeatable results (we adopted 100). The electricity consumption for the cell is therefore found by finding the average electricity consumption per household in the simulated group, and multiplying this average by the estimated number of households in the cell.

The results of applying this method to the Zambia datasets are shown in Figure 4. For urban areas (Figure 4a), the average rwi for the groups of households in the cells is between about -1 and 1. According to our method, the corresponding average household electricity consumption is in the range 500 - 2,400 kWh/year, with an overall average of 2,000 kWh/year across all urban cells that have electricity access. This value seems in line with the electricity consumption provided by (Mulongoti et al. 2016) for the Kitwe city. This city, the second largest after the capital Lusaka in Zambia, is located in the Copperbelt province, one of the wealthiest in Zambia. In this study, they report that, during load shedding events in 2015, the electricity consumption amounted to 1,348 kWh on average, while before the load shedding, the projections amounted to 1,659 kWh.

For rural areas (Figure 4b), the average rwi for the groups of households in the cells is substantially lower, mostly between -1 to 0. While some individual households exhibit very high wealth index (above 3), leading to correspondingly high electricity consumption (blue dots on the right side of the bottom graph), the average rwi values imply that there must be very few of these high-consumption households in any given cell, if any. In addition, wi is computed separately for urban and rural areas (Trevor N., Courtney K., Blake W., et al. 2023) and appliance ownership is much lower in rural households than for urban households with the same wi . These factors together lead to lower average household electricity consumption in the rural cells (that have access) of 80 kWh/year.

The distribution of the average relative wealth index rwi of each of the cells in our dataset (in purple) is concentrated in a smaller value range than the distribution of wealth index wi for individual households in the DHS survey (blue). This concentration would be expected for any distribution of group averages where the groups are diverse, and as shown it is possible to create a set of “simulated” groups of households from the DHS dataset that has a similar concentrated distribution.

Figure 4 Household density and annual energy consumption against their wealth index in urban (a) and rural (b) areas. In the scatter graphs, blue circles represent the assessed energy consumption of the individual households in the DHS dataset, with size proportional to the statistical weighting⁹ assigned in the original dataset. Orange diamonds represent the averages for each simulated group of households selected from the DHS dataset to simulate the map cells. The histograms

⁹ For each household in the DHS dataset, a weighting factor is given that adjusts for differences in probability of selection of the household within the area. This weight is used when analysis of the data is performed in order to have the best possible representation of the area.

in the upper panels show the distributions of these as a function of wealth index (blue lines and orange bars respectively), together with the distribution of the average relative wealth index values for each map cell (purple line) for comparison.

2.1.3. Final assessment

The total residential energy consumption per hexagon cell is obtained by multiplying the average estimated consumption for the cell by the number of electrified households in this cell. In applications of this method where it is necessary that the total estimated electricity usage is exactly equal to a total from another source (e.g. national or regional electricity demand data), the residential energy use can simply be scaled to compensate for the energy uses not included in the survey and any other limitations to the approach.

2.2. Services: a top-down approach based on occupations

Analysis at the province level

From the DHS survey on characteristics of respondents (e) (Zambia Statistics Agency, Ministry of Health (MOH) Zambia, and ICF 2020), the share of women and men working in the following occupations is extracted: Professional/technical/managerial, clerical, sales and services, and skilled manual. The shares are computed per province p and per area type (urban u or rural r), noted for instance $ShareW_{r,p,f}$ for women f in rural areas, and are based on the population aged 15-49 employed in the 12 months preceding the survey by occupation.

Analysis at the cell level

Population data at the cell level, obtained with the residential analysis, are disaggregated by sex using the national population gender ratio provided in the census by Zamstats (Zamstats 2022) and are noted for instance $P_{hex,f}$ for the female f population. To estimate the number of employees W_{hex} in each hexagon cell, the female f and male m populations are multiplied by their respective labour force participation shares $ShareW_{r,p,f}$, as noted in equation (5) for rural areas:

$$W_{hex} = P_{hex,f} * ShareW_{r,p,f} + P_{hex,m} * ShareW_{r,p,m} \quad (5)$$

Finally, total services sector electricity consumption from the UN statistics is allocated to each cell with an electrified status proportionally to the estimated number of employees. This approach leads to an electricity consumption per employee of 323 kWh. The electrified status of the cell is a binary value, 0 if the cell is electrified, 1 if not. The cell is considered electrified if the probability given by the HREA dataset is greater than a threshold value set at 90% and 10% for urban and rural areas respectively.

2.3. Industry methodology: a bottom-up assessment

Zambia's industrial sector energy consumption is mainly driven by the mining industry. The mining sector plays a significant role in the economy, representing around 15% of GDP (Mulder et al. 2024) and around 70% of export earnings (PWC 2024). The main metal produced is copper, with cobalt as a by-product. With an annual copper mine production between 750 and 850 kt in the last few years, Zambia ranks among the 10 largest producers of mined copper globally (US Geological Survey 2024b). Although Zambia possesses considerable cobalt reserves (US Geological Survey 2024a), cobalt production has decreased in the last decade from around 5 kt mine production in 2014 (US

Geological Survey 2016) to 0.2 kt in 2021 (US Geological Survey 2024e). Other produced metals include gold, manganese and nickel but they operate on a much smaller scale with an average mine production of respectively 4 t (0.1% of global production)(US Geological Survey 2023), 96 kt (0.5% of global production) (US Geological Survey 2024f) and 3 kt (0.1% of global production) (US Geological Survey 2024d) in the period from 2018 till 2022.

According to the United Nations (UN) Statistics data (UNSD 2024) in 2019, 93% of electricity consumption and 53% of oil consumption in the industry sector were linked to the non-ferrous metal and mining and quarrying subsectors. To geographically distribute this energy consumption, production steps and their associated energy demand are separated. The study focuses on the main consumption subsector, copper production and completes the industrial demand mapping by considering cobalt, gold, manganese and nickel production.

To assess the electricity consumption of the mining sector, a bottom-up methodology is applied, leveraging geospatially located data on mining processes. This data from USGS (Padilla et al. 2021) provides a comprehensive GIS dataset encompassing the locations, site names, product type and production capacities of most mining sites across Zambia. The product types in this dataset distinguish between ores, concentrates and metals processed. The production capacities reported in this dataset correspond to the year 2017. Electricity demands per site are first estimated per metal produced and then summarized and adjusted to accurately represent the overall demand, taking into account production level for the year 2019.

2.3.1. Copper production energy demand

Zambia mainly produces primary copper (US Geological Survey 2024c). Two main parts of the production are ore mining and metal processing. Most energy-intensive steps of the ore mining are extraction and transport of the ore to the processing plant and comminution of the ore rocks (Allen 2021). Other processes such as filtering, drying and flotation, are less energy intensive. Ore extraction and transport mining equipment (haul trucks, excavators, drills, loaders etc.), generally use diesel or other liquid fuels to power them. Extraction of the ore can take place in open-pit or underground mines. Usually, open pit operation is used for mining low-grade ores (around 0.5%), whereas underground operation is suited for higher ore grades (1-2%) (Moreno-Leiva et al. 2020). In open pit mines, the age of the plant will additionally influence the energy consumption: as material is gradually extracted from deeper and deeper, the transporting equipment will need to cover increasing distances to reach the extraction depth. In underground mines, the fuel usage is reduced, and electricity is used mainly for ventilation (Moreno-Leiva et al. 2020). The comminution step requires energy for ore crushing and grinding, work of the pumps etc. therefore electrical energy is utilised (Allen 2021).

Depending on the ore type, there are two main metal processing routes, as depicted in Figure 5. Sulfide ore is utilized in the pyrometallurgical route whereas oxide ore is utilised in the hydrometallurgical route. Sulfide ore is first subjected to fine milling and then concentrated through a flotation process. Copper concentrate usually has a copper grade of 25-35% (Frischenschlager et al. 2010). In order to obtain nearly pure copper, the following processes are implemented, progressively increasing the copper content: smelting (approx. 65% copper content), converting by oxidation (blister copper 98%), fire refining and anode casting by reduction (anode copper 99%), electrorefining by electrolysis (cathode copper 99.95-99.99%) (Moreno-Leiva et al. 2020; Hübner et al. 2020). The hydrometallurgical route does not require milling to be as fine as in the pyrometallurgical route since crushed ore undergoes the leaching process, where copper is leached from the rock to the solution (Moreno-Leiva et al. 2020). After the concentrated solution undergoes the solvent extraction (SX) process, cathode copper is finally obtained by electrowinning (EW).

Figure 5 Copper transformation steps and the copper content in respective processes

Thus, energy consumption of each copper site is determined by several factors including the mine type, mine age and location, ore grade, metal processing route as well as process design and chosen equipment (e.g. smelting, converting and flotation). These factors are quantified in the first step of our energy assessment, whereas in the next steps electricity and diesel consumptions of each mining site are assessed based on the production level and the energy intensity of the processes associated to that site.

In the first step, for each of the processes of the copper mining production, a thorough literature review determines the associated energy intensity, as illustrated in Table 2. The literature provides energy intensities per ton of copper produced. However, the USGS GIS dataset mostly provides data on capacity of processed ore and processed concentrate in tons of ore and tons of concentrated copper, respectively. Therefore, the ore and concentrate grades need to be assessed.

The average ore grade g_{avg} of mines in Zambia was calculated by weighting the average mill grade $g_{mill,i}$ of each mine i reported in (S&P Capital IQ 2024) with the quantity of its milled ore $Q_{mill,i}$, see equation (6). When the average mill grade of a mine was unavailable, it was calculated by dividing the current copper production capacity with the ore milling capacity of that mine. If these values were unavailable, the average mill grade of a mine was set equal to the mine's mill grade of the most recent year, if possible. Average ore grade of Zambian mines was calculated to be 1.03%. The concentrate grade was assumed to be 30% (Frischenschlager et al. 2010).

$$g_{avg} = \frac{\sum_i g_{mill,i} \cdot Q_{mill,i}}{\sum_i Q_{mill,i}}$$

(6)

Table 2 Copper production processes and their energy intensities

Product type	Process	Process type	Electricity intensity [MWh/t _{cu}]	Reference
Ore and concentrate	Mining	Open pit	-	(Moreno-Leiva et al. 2020)
Ore and concentrate	Mining	Underground	0.60	(Moreno-Leiva et al. 2020)
Ore and concentrate	Milling		2.67	(Allen 2021)

Metal	Smelting	Flash smelting, flash converting	2.57	(Coursol et al. 2015)
Metal	Smelting	Isasmelt, Peirce Smith converting (PSC)	1.92	(Coursol et al. 2015)
Metal	Smelting	Mitsubishi Process	2.36	(Coursol et al. 2015)
Metal	Smelting	Noranda–Teniente	2.80	(Coursol et al. 2015)
Metal	Smelting	Noranda reactor, PSC	2.48	(Coursol et al. 2015)
Metal	Smelting	Bottom blowing smelting, PSC	2.57	(Coursol et al. 2015)
Metal	Smelting	Reverberatory furnace	0.60	(Coursol et al. 2015)
Metal	Refining	Electro-refining	0.36	(Moreno-Leiva et al. 2020)
Metal	Leaching, SX EW		3.47	(Allen 2021)

Production levels per site are determined in the second step. Initially, for each site the product type is verified and eventually adapted based on the additionally provided notes in the USGS GIS dataset, in order to address the production capacity in the correct unit (tons of ore, concentrate or metal) and to afterwards correctly select the associated production processes. After verification, no sites had “concentrate” as their product type. Next, negative capacity values in the USGS GIS dataset, which signal that capacity data are not included in the dataset, are set to 0. However, for the Kansanshi mine and Sentinel mine, we were able to substitute production level data that were available for the year 2022 from an alternative source (First Quantum Minerals Ltd 2023a; 2023b) . Furthermore, for each product type, a usage rate is assessed so that the total production for the year 2019 matches the total production reported by USGS in their Minerals Yearbook (US Geological Survey 2024c). The combined ore and concentrate production is matched with mined copper, whereas combined metal production is matched with refined copper, implying usage rates of 77% and 31%, respectively. Moreover, production data from USGS yearly reports and energy intensities are expressed in tonnes of copper content. Thus, to estimate the produced copper tonnage, the assessed production levels of ores and concentrates are multiplied by their respective average grades.

In the third step, production processes are associated to each site, as well as their specific type based on the site name¹⁰. For example, if the site name contains words such as “facility” or “plant”, we assumed that the site contains both a smelter and a refinery process, whereas having explicitly “smelter” or a “refinery” in the name would suggest that only the respective process intensity should be considered. To specific the type of production, the site name was searched for words that would indicate this. For example, in a smelting site, “Isasmelt”, “Mitsubishi”, “Flash” etc. would be

¹⁰ Additional notes partly provide the information if the output product was anode or cathode copper. However, this information does not specify the starting copper product or the production route. Thus, the note does not reveal (all) involved processes. If available, this information was therefore used for the validation of the assumptions.

indicative of the process. In the case that no further information can be extracted, the default types are used, namely an underground mine for mining sites, and flash smelting for a smelting site.

Finally, in the fourth step, for each site the produced copper tonnage was multiplied by the sum of the corresponding process energy intensities per tonne.

2.3.2. Cobalt, gold, nickel and manganese production energy demand

Following a similar procedure as for copper, the energy required for cobalt, gold, nickel and manganese production was estimated.

The first step determines energy intensity per tonne of the produced metal. Globally, cobalt is mainly extracted as by-product of nickel mining (about 55%) and copper mining (about 35%) (Sverdrup, Ragnarsdottir, and Koca 2017). Cobalt ore in Zambia is produced in the same mines as copper and nickel and thus mainly shares their capacity in the USGS GIS dataset. Moreover, cobalt ore grade significantly differs across the Zambian mines (Dehaine et al. 2021). Thus, only the metal production process is considered for the cobalt production. Furthermore, the USGS GIS dataset gives information on production capacities for gold, nickel and manganese in Zambia directly as a mass of metal content. Therefore, no estimation of ore or concentrate grade is necessary. Energy intensities for each metal and production process are given in Table 3.

According to the literature survey from (Allen 2021), the total energy consumption per ton of produced gold for mining and metal processing considerably differs for underground (37.22 MWh/kg) and open pit mines (103.33 MWh/kg), due to the typically higher ore grade in underground mines. The metal processing part in the gold production contains cyanide leaching, carbon loading, electrowinning and tailings management (Allen 2021). Energy intensity of the nickel sulfide mining operations does not differ significantly between the underground and open pit mines (Allen 2021), wherefore an average value from that source was taken.

*Table 3 Cobalt, gold, nickel and manganese production processes and their energy intensities. Values marked by * represent total energy intensity instead of electricity intensity.*

Material	Product type	Process (type)	Electricity intensity [MWh/t _{cu}]	Reference
Cobalt	Metal	Refining	3.77	(van der Meide et al. 2022)
Gold	Ore and concentrate	Mining (Open pit)	-	(Allen 2021)
Gold	Ore and concentrate	Mining (Underground)	$6.70 \cdot 10^3$	(Allen 2021)
Gold	Ore and concentrate	Milling (Open pit)	$26.86 \cdot 10^3$	(Allen 2021)
Gold	Ore and concentrate	Milling (Underground)	$9.67 \cdot 10^3$	(Allen 2021)
Gold	Metal	Processing (Open pit)	$14.47 \cdot 10^3$ *	(Allen 2021)
Gold	Metal	Processing (Underground)	$10.79 \cdot 10^3$ *	(Allen 2021)

Nickel	Ore and concentrate	Mining, Milling	5.00	(Allen 2021)
Nickel	Metal	Smelting, Refining	55.56 *	(Allen 2021)
Manganese	Ore and concentrate	Milling	0.01	(Farjana et al. 2019)
Manganese	Metal	Refining	5.00	(Farjana et al. 2019)

In the next steps energy usage per site is determined. A usage rate of produced materials is calculated so that the sum of the site capacities from the USGS GIS dataset multiplied with the usage rate fits the national production amounts from the USGS mineral yearbooks. Next, appropriate electricity intensity per site and material is selected. As the USGS GIS dataset contains no additional information regarding gold mine type, the authors use the average value. Finally, the multiplication of the production capacity, usage rate and energy intensity deliver the final energy estimates.

2.3.3. Summarising and adjusting energy demand

The energy consumption of all sites are then scaled so that the combined total energy use matches the total electricity consumption of non-ferrous and mining sector for the year 2019 based on UN statistics data (UNSD 2024) to ensure the accuracy and representativeness of the overall assessment.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Buildings

Figure 6, Figure 7, and Figure 8 present the electricity consumption in the residential, services, and building sectors, respectively. Table 4 summarizes electricity consumption by sector and province.

The residential bottom-up approach leads to a total of 2,210 GWh for all the cells. We would expect our approach to produce an underestimate because the DHS survey does not capture all electricity uses. Bearing that in mind, this total is not completely inconsistent with the total residential demand reported by the UN statistics of 4,023 GWh for 2019 (UNSD 2024), however the difference is significant and presents a challenge to datasets we are using. It may be that the appliance energies in Table 1 are underestimated and are much higher in reality. The relative wealth index estimates from the remote sensing and AI may also be underestimating the real average wealth index on the ground. Further work to understand and quantify the origins of the difference between our bottom-up approach and national totals could lead to improvements in the remote sensing approach, as well as understanding of real energy usage, access and equality. To match the UN statistics, the scaling factor applied to residential electricity consumption amounts to 182%. Table 4 includes the results before and after scaling for the residential sector.

Looking at the spatial characteristics of energy consumption in buildings, most of the energy consumption is located in the capital city, Lusaka, and in the Copperbelt region, which concentrates most of the mining activities and thus is a wealthier province compared to the others.

Figure 6 Electricity consumption in the residential sector (kWh) The red intensity corresponds to the electricity consumption in the residential sector in kWh on a logarithmic scale. Purple lines are the Zambian transmission lines.

Figure 7 **Electricity consumption in services (kWh)** The red intensity corresponds to the electricity consumption in the service sector in kWh on a logarithmic scale. Purple lines are the Zambian transmission lines.

Figure 8 **Electricity consumption in the buildings sector (kWh)** The red intensity corresponds to the electricity consumption in the buildings sector in kWh on a logarithmic scale. Purple lines are the Zambian transmission lines.

Table 4 **Electricity consumption per region and per sector in 2019 (GWh)**

Province	Residential		Services	Buildings	Share (buildings)
	before scaling	after scaling			
Central	130	236	60	297	6%
Copperbelt	691	1,257	176	1,433	30%
Eastern	86	156	51	208	4%
Luapula	38	69	29	98	2%
Lusaka	855	1,556	211	1,767	37%
Muchinga	25	45	14	60	1%
North-Western	103	187	46	233	5%
Northern	71	129	29	158	3%
Southern	161	293	75	368	8%
Western	51	93	31	124	3%
Zambia	2,210	4,023	722	4,744	100%

Total electricity consumption

To assess the accuracy of our spatially disaggregated results, the electricity consumption estimates at the province level are compared with data from CIGZ (Cities and Infrastructure for Growth Zambia)¹¹. However, some discrepancies emerged between this data source and the UN statistics, both in overall electricity consumption and sector-specific breakdowns (Table 5). CIGZ data, for instance, only provides a breakdown between the mining sector and the rest while UN statistics have a much more detailed breakdown. For instance, CIGZ energy consumption for mining likely corresponds only to the “Non-ferrous metals” sub-sector in the UN statistics, which amounts to 6,360 GWh, very close to the 6,388 GWh from CIGZ. Including the additional “Mining and quarrying” sub-sector (227 GWh) in the UN statistics results in a total of 6,588 GWh for the mining industry.

Comparing our model's building-sector consumption estimates with the data from CIGZ (Table 6), we observe relatively similar shares in most provinces, with differences typically within a few percentage points. Notable discrepancies occur in Lusaka and Copperbelt provinces. Our model arrives at lower consumption in Lusaka compared to CIGZ, while arriving at higher consumption in Copperbelt. This difference could be attributed to inclusion of non-building sectors in the CIGZ data, particularly agriculture, non-specified sectors, and quarrying. The presence of significant quarrying activity in the Copperbelt region likely contributes to the higher consumption figures reported by CIGZ in that province.

Table 5 Electricity consumption per sector in 2019 (GWh)

	CIGZ data (GWh)	UN stats (GWh)
Total	13,250	12,341
Mining	6,388	6,588
Other	6,862	5,753
<i>Buildings</i>		4,744
<i>Other</i>		1,009

Table 6 Electricity consumption per province in 2019 (GWh)

Province	CIGZ data (GWh)	Buildings - This study (GWh)	Share CIGZ	Share Buildings
Central	500	297	7%	6%
Copperbelt	1,843	1,433	27%	30%
North-Western	135	233	2%	5%
Eastern	179	208	3%	4%
Luapula	77	98	1%	2%
Lusaka	3,409	1,767	50%	37%
Muchinga	64	60	1%	1%
Northern	92	158	1%	3%
Southern	492	368	7%	8%
Western	70	124	1%	3%
Zambia	6,862	4,744		

¹¹ Data has been provided through personal communication.

To further validate our approach, we compare our residential electricity consumption estimate with a direct estimate derived from the DHS survey. In Section 2.1.2, we assigned an electricity consumption value to each household in the DHS dataset. Each household is representative of the whole country, as defined by a sampling weight. We calculate two average consumption figures depending on the inclusion of households without electricity access. The first average, 516 kWh, represents the overall average consumption across *all* surveyed households, including those without electricity access. The second average, 1,511 kWh, represents the average consumption *only* for households reporting electricity access. Multiplying these averages by the respective total number of households (all households for the 516 kWh calculation and households with access for the 1,511 kWh calculation) yields estimated total consumption figures of 1,893 GWh and 2,579 GWh. These DHS-derived estimates bracket our bottom-up estimate of 2,210 GWh, lending further support to its validity.

Electricity access rates

Our methodology results depend on the quality of the data input. In particular, for electricity access rates, our number of households with access to electricity are computed with probability given by the HREA dataset. Table 9 presents electricity access rates for 2019 obtained with the above methodology, compared against data from various sources: World Bank (World Bank 2023), IEA (IEA 2023a), the Multi-Tier Framework (MTF) survey (Luzi et al. 2019), the Demographic and Health Survey (DHS) (Zambia Statistics Agency et al. 2020) and the Gridded Dataset for Electrification in Sub-Saharan Africa (GDESSA) (Falchetta et al. 2019). While the considered year is 2019, data for the DHS and GDESSA are from 2018. This comparison reveals significant uncertainties in electricity access rate estimations, as recently highlighted by (Hirmer et al. 2024). Although the rates can be assessed at the household or population level, the differences between the two are less than 2% percentage point in the DHS survey. This suggests that the values for both levels are likely to be close and fall within the overall uncertainty range. For urban areas, the MTF, World Bank and the DHS report rates around 75%, while rural rates amount to around 12%. At the national level, a 10-percentage point discrepancy exists between the IEA and DHS values (around 33%) and those reported by the MTF and World Bank (around 43%). Our methodology yields a slight overestimation of rural access at 23%, resulting in a marginally higher overall national electrification rate compared to the one given by the MTF and World Bank. This could thus lead to a slightly higher estimate of electricity consumption in rural areas if our assessment based on HREA is reliable.

Figure 9 Electricity access rate at the national level by area type

Electricity access rates can also be analysed by consumption tiers, corresponding to different levels of energy consumption as defined in the MTF classification (Bhatia and Angelou 2015). Both the MTF and GDESSA provide tiers breakdown, although GDESSA groups tier 4 and 5 as tier 4. While significant discrepancies exist in the tier distribution across these two sources, the inherent uncertainties in these data limit the reliability of any single source for validation.

Comparing our results against the MTF, we find a similar overall electricity access rate for rural areas, with most of the population falling into Tier 1. For urban areas, we observe a higher overall access rate, but our model predicts a more concentrated distribution of the population within Tier 4, unlike the more dispersed distribution across tiers in the MTF survey. However, when comparing our results against GDESSA, we observe a similar distribution of tiers, except for the Tier 0 which seems to be under assessed given the national electricity access rates in urban areas from the other sources (see Table 9).

Figure 10 Electricity access rates per tier.

Note: In the MTF data, the value for Tier 0 is higher than in the table with national access rates, as some households with

electricity access do not meet Tier 1 requirement. In the GDESSA dataset, only 4 tiers are included, Tier 4 corresponds to Tier 4 and 5 from the MTF classification.

3.2. Industry

The final industry results are shown on Figure 11, which presents a map of industrial electricity consumptions summed per hexagon. Since industrial demand is allocated to the metal producing sites, it is distributed among a couple of the hexagon regions.

Figure 11 Assessed industrial electricity demand per hexagon. The map shows sparsely distributed electricity demand allocated to the mining and metal production sites.

To validate the approach, the industry results before scaling are compared with the UN energy balance statistics. Total estimated electricity demand for the copper mining and metal production for 2019 sums up to 4.5 TWh (see Figure 12 on the left side), covering thus 69% of the Zambian non-ferrous and mining sectors' electricity demand from the UN statistics (UNSD 2024) (see Figure 12 in the middle). Including other metals produced in Zambia further increases the electricity consumption coverage rate. The calculated electricity demand for non-ferrous and mining sector in 2019 sums up to 5.2 TWh, covering in total 79% of the corresponding electricity demand from the UN statistics. The observed difference could stem from a range of factors: for example, it could result from a lower efficiency of real processes compared to the ones we have assumed, since the literature values are not specifically representative of Zambia's industry. Moreover, a likely source of discrepancy is the relatively simplified bottom-up representation of the processes, therefore neglecting additional site-related electricity consumption like lighting, plant monitoring, water treatment etc. Furthermore, we note that the UN energy balance only includes electricity entries for non-ferrous metals, mining and quarrying, and a negligible electricity consumption (0.1%) for construction industry, but it is apparent from economic data that other industries are also present in

Zambia. Although there is a small portion of 6.6% of the electricity consumption assigned to the industry consumption not elsewhere specified, it is possible that energy consumption in these other industries has been incorrectly attributed to non-ferrous metals and mining and quarrying.

Furthermore, while not a discrepancy in aggregate energy consumption, a clear allocation discrepancy exists between our estimation and UN statistics regarding the relative electricity consumption of the mining and the non-ferrous sector. UN statistics attributes almost all electricity consumption to the non-ferrous sector, whereas our study estimates roughly the same electricity shares for both subsectors. The difference likely comes from different attribution of processes to the subsectors in the two sources used – USGS GIS dataset and UN statistics. Specifically, ore milling and concentration, an electricity-intensive process, is in this study associated with the mining sector, whereas it may be associated with the non-ferrous sector in UN statistics.

Figure 12 Total estimated mining industries electricity consumption before scaling (left) and coverage rates in comparison to the UN statistics (middle) with the shares of other metals in the coverage rate (right)

4. Conclusion

This study presents a new methodology for highly spatially disaggregated electricity demand assessment in the buildings and industry sectors of Zambia. For industry and residential buildings, a bottom-up approach is employed, based on the combination of GIS datasets and data provided at the national level. A top-down approach, leveraging the DHS dataset, provides spatial disaggregation for the services sector. Discrepancies emerge between our bottom-up estimates and the national statistics, which can either be explained by the GIS data quality (for instance in the case of electricity access rates, the quality of the HREA dataset) or by the limitations of other input data, for instance in terms of appliance coverage in the DHS survey. To reconcile these discrepancies and ensure alignment with the UN statistics, results can be scaled and other alternative allocation methods are detailed in Supplementary Material (8.3). In this case, for the residential sector, the link between the wealth index and the energy consumption is assumed to be a sigmoid curve, which is then adjusted to match the national statistics. In addition, for the services sector, another method based on allocation of the electricity consumption per building instead of per employee is presented in Supplementary Material 8.4. This method can be used if the DHS survey is not available for the country.

The method based on open-source data is replicable in other countries. Thus, future research will extend this methodology to other LMICs with available DHS survey data. Additional sectors can be included, for instance agriculture, for which crops and irrigation could be used as a proxy for electricity consumption, as well as other energy-intensive industrial sectors. By leveraging the identified sector-specific drivers for demand, projections of electricity demand can also be undertaken. For example, future industrial electricity demand can be assessed based on new mining operations and projected production levels of key minerals (e.g., copper, cobalt).

In addition, the high spatial resolution of our electricity demand estimates can contribute to several crucial applications, particularly for achieving Sustainable Development Goal 7 (Affordable and Clean Energy) and 10 (Reduced Inequalities). From our spatially electricity demand for a base year, the demand can be projected by including household size growth, urbanisation and relative wealth index (RWI) trends. The resulting spatially explicit demand projections can provide valuable inputs for power system models, informing grid planning and infrastructure investment decisions or decentralized generation planning. Incorporating appliance-specific demand profile, particularly for cooling, can also inform strategies to manage peak demand. Demand projections can also include an assessment of the latent electricity demand for households without access, based on the relationship between consumption and the RWI of the area described in our methodology. This facilitates targeted electrification planning in areas with high unmet need. Finally, by linking electricity consumption with RWI trends and other socioeconomic indicators (e.g., gender data), this research can also provide valuable insights into the socio-economic distributional impact of energy transitions, impacts on marginalised groups and energy poverty and thus contribute to more equitable energy access.

5. Data availability

The list of data used for the analysis is described in Supplementary Material 8.1. They are all open-source and can directly be downloaded. The code to run the analysis is available at https://github.com/ariane-millot/EDeMOS_Zambia and the results data at <https://zenodo.org/records/14285097> and can be visualised at <https://endemmap-spider.github.io/>.

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8. Supplementary Materials

8.1. List of input data

Table 7 List of input data

Spatial type	Sector	Input Dataset	Data type	Resolution	Description	Link	Coordinate
Spatial data	Industry	Mine location	vector		This geodatabase contains the georeferenced locations of mineral commodity production and processing facilities, mineral exploration and development sites, and mineral commodity exporting ports in Africa.	https://www.usgs.gov/d ata/compilation-geospatial-data-gis-mineral-industries-and-related-infrastructure-africa	WGS84
	Building	Building location	raster	approximately 100m (3 arc seconds)	Worldpop: this raster contains counts of buildings that fall within a grid cell. Each buildings was counted in the grid cell that contained the centroid of its building footprint	https://wopr.worldpop.org/?ZMB	WGS84
		Urban areas	raster	approximately 100m (3 arc seconds)	Worldpop: This raster contains an urban / rural classification for each grid cell based on building patterns in their surroundings.	https://wopr.worldpop.org/?ZMB	WGS84
		High Resolution Electricity Access	raster	1 or 7.5 arcsec depending on the area	The HREA are derived from statistical processing of nightly satellite observations of the earth at night and gives the predicted likelihood that a settlement is electrified (0 to 1)	https://hrea.isr.umich.edu/data.html	WGS84
		RWI	raster	2.4km resolution	The Relative Wealth Index predicts the relative standard of living within countries using de-identified connectivity data, satellite imagery and other nontraditional data sources.	https://data.humdata.org/dataset/relative-wealth-index	EPSG:3857
	All	Administrative boundaries	vector		GADM map the administrative areas of all countries, at all levels of sub-division.	https://gadm.org/maps/ZMB.html	WGS84

Non spatial data	Building	Census data			Population census of the country	https://www.zamstats.gov.zm/2022-census/	
		DHS survey			The DHS survey provides data for planning, implementation, and monitoring and evaluation of national health programmes.	https://dhsprogram.com/methodology/survey/survey-display-542.cfm	
	All	UN stats			Energy balance provided by UN Statistics Division	https://data.un.org/SdxmxBrowser/start	

8.2. Residential assumptions

(Bhatia and Angelou 2015; MECS 2020) give annual minimum energy consumption, so the consumptions were adjusted to get an average energy consumption for each tier.

Table 8 Average annual consumption (kWh) adjusted from (Bhatia and Angelou 2015; MECS 2020)

Appliance	Tier 1			Tier 2			Tier 3			Tier 4			Tier 5		
	Watts	hours/day	Average cons. (kWh)												
Electricity	1	4	4	37	6	222	54	8	432	54	10	870	54	18	1302
Mobile telephone	2	2	4	2	4	8	2	4	8	2	4	8	2	4	8
Radio	2	2	4	4	4	16	4	4	16	4	4	16	4	4	16
Television	0	0	0	20	2	40	40	2	80	40	2	80	40	2	80
Microwave	0	0	0	0	0	0	500	0.2	100	500	0.2	100	500	0.2	100
Washing machine	0	0	0	0	0	0	500	0.5	250	500	0.5	250	500	0.5	250
Refrigerator	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	300	3	900	300	3	900
Air conditioner	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1000	2	2000

8.3. Method to assess the residential electricity consumption based on an analogue mapping from wealth index to electricity consumption

8.3.1. Methodology derived from the Zambian case

In section 2.1.2 we presented our method for mapping the average relative wealth index (rwi) of map cells to average household energy consumption using DHS survey data (E_{hh}). The relationship between electricity consumption and rwi that was revealed by this method can also be represented by a mathematical function:

$$E_{hh} = \frac{A f_{elec}}{1 + e^{-k(rwi - rwi_0)}} \quad (7)$$

where:

- E_{hh} : average electricity consumption of household group
- rwi : average relative wealth index of group
- f_{elec} : the number of households in group with electricity access
- A, k, rwi_0 : free parameters constrained by fitting to the data

An unconstrained fit of this equation to simulated groups of households from the DHS is shown in Figure 13. The value of $E_{threshold}$ given by the fit is 4,302 kWh, which compares favourably with a manual estimate of 4,656 kWh based on a bottom-up assessment of electricity consumption for a set of appliances for Tier 5 as defined in the ESMAP report on energy access (Bhatia and Angelou 2015) and (MECS 2020).

The curve closely replicates the relationship of the groups and so allows our method to be applied to regions or countries where suitable household survey data is not available. In these cases, the parameters in equation (7) can be constrained by other data such as the national/regional total consumption or set equal to the equivalent parameter values for similar countries. This analogue approach can also be used as a faster computational alternative to creating subsamples for tens of thousands of map cells.

Figure 13 The fitting function from equation (7) applied to map the average group relative wealth index of simulated groups to the average household electricity consumption of those groups. The upper panel shows groups formed from the urban household dataset where the access rate is quite high and does not vary much. The lower panel shows rural regions where the access rate varies much more.

8.3.2. Methodology to match national statistics

An alternative method is presented in this section that aims to provide an electricity assessment that will automatically match the national statistics. It relies on defining the relationship between the relative wealth index (rwi) provided by (Data for Good at Meta 2021) to the electricity consumption. In each cell, we have the number of households with electricity access, as well as the average rwi value.

After normalising the rwi values of the cells that include households with access to electricity, the relationship between electricity consumption and rwi is modelling using a sigmoidal (S-curve) function:

$$E_{hh} = \frac{E_{threshold}}{1 + \alpha e^{-k rwi}}$$

with:

- E_{hh} : electricity consumption per household

- $E_{threshold}$: the maximum value for the electricity consumption, set to 4656 kWh based on a bottom-up assessment of electricity consumption for a set of appliances as defined in the ESMAP report on energy access (Bhatia and Angelou 2015) and (MECS 2020).
- α : a parameter calibrated to ensure a consumption of 7 kWh for the lowest rwi values, consistent with the sources used for $E_{threshold}$
- k : parameter representing the steepness of the curve
- rwi : relative wealth index

The parameter k is optimised such that the product of the calculated per-household electricity consumption and the number of households with electricity access matches the total residential electricity consumption reported by the UN statistics. The resulting relationship for Zambia is shown on Figure 14.

Figure 14 Electricity consumption per household vs normalised RWI

8.4. Assessment based on buildings for the service sector

The number of service buildings is computed based on the total number of buildings and residential buildings that have been determined during the residential electricity consumption assessment (see section 2.1) with the following equation for instance in rural areas:

$$serBui_{r,p} = Bui_{r,p} - resBui_{r,p}$$

(8)

By multiplying this number with the electricity access probability (d), the number of services buildings with electricity access is determined. The total services electricity consumption from the UN statistics is then allocated proportionally to the number of service buildings with access to electricity in each cell.

In order to get the final electricity services consumption, a weighted average between the two methods is computed.

8.5. Additional results for the residential sector

Table 9 Electricity access rate at the national level

Year 2019	MTF	World Bank	IEA	DHS - 2018		GDESSA - 2018	This study
	Household	Population	Population	Population	Household	Household	Household
Urban	76%	79%	NA	71%	69%	98%	82%
Rural	12%	14%	NA	8%	8%	13%	23%
Total	42%	43%	34%	33%	34%	49%	49%

Table 10 Electricity access rates per tier.

Note: In the MTF data, the value for Tier 0 is higher than in the table with national access rates, as some households with electricity access don't meet tier 1 requirement. In the GDESSA dataset, only 4 tiers are included, tier 4 corresponds to tier 4 and 5 from the MTF classification.

Tier	MTF			GDESSA - 2018			This study		
	Total	Urban	Rural	Total	Urban	Rural	Total	Urban	Rural
0	60%	25%	91%	51%	1%	87%	52%	18%	77%
1	2%	1%	4%	4%	2%	6%	13%	0%	23%
2	2%	2%	1%	4%	6%	3%	1%	1%	0%
3	8%	16%	1%	6%	10%	2%	5%	11%	0%
4	7%	15%	1%	35%	81%	2%	27%	64%	0%
5	21%	42%	2%				3%	6%	0%